

QhX / AGN Catalogue Portal – Technical Documentation

Authors: Milena Stanković Cerović¹

¹ Independent Researcher, Belgrade, Serbia

² Faculty of Mathematics, University of Belgrade, Serbia

³ Faculty of Science, University of Kragujevac, Kragujevac, Serbia

⁴ Astronomical Observatory, Belgrade, Serbia

Last updated: 2026-1-14 – version 0.2.1

Abstract

The QhX / AGN Catalogue Portal is a PHP-based web platform that serves as the technical interface to a secondary catalogue of active galactic nuclei (AGNs) extracted from Vera C. Rubin Observatory LSST Data Preview 1 (DP1) and processed with the Quasar harmonic eXplorer (QhX, v0.2.1) pipeline. The portal provides authenticated users with interactive catalogue search and browsing, object detail views, exploratory visualisation modules (sky and parameter-space views), and Virtual Observatory (VO) compatible data access via VOTable export for TOPCAT and a Simple Cone Search (SCS) endpoint for pyVO. Access to VO services is controlled through short-lived JWT tokens with database-backed audit trails and optional constraints (one-time use, IP locking). In addition, the portal implements a controlled in-kind ingestion workflow for externally contributed Parquet catalogues, including Docker-based Python validation, staging tables, and an auditable promotion mechanism into the canonical QhX tables. This Zenodo record provides a versioned, citable technical reference of the portal's architecture, data model, security mechanisms, and ingestion pipeline to support reproducibility, maintainability, and transparent reuse by the broader community.

Keywords: quasars, active galactic nuclei, time-domain astronomy, photometric variability, coherent oscillations, quasi-periodic oscillations, red noise, non-stationary time series, time-frequency analysis, Hilbert space methods, LSST, Rubin Observatory, astronomical catalogues, Virtual Observatory

Quick Overview

What is the QhX / AGN Catalogue Portal?

The QhX / AGN Catalogue Portal is a PHP-based web portal for a secondary catalogue of AGNs, grouped by the type of oscillatory signal present in their light curves, taken from the Vera C. Rubin Observatory - Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) Data Preview 1 (DP1), derived with the Quasar harmonic eXplorer (QhX, v0.2.1) pipeline.

The QhX / AGN Catalogue Portal is developed within the Rubin In-kind Contribution SER-SAG-S1 "Science Pipeline Development for analysis of variability of celestial sources in the LSST AGN and TVS Science Collaboration" (Contribution Lead: A. Kovacevic).

It provides interactive web tools for catalogue search and browsing, visualisation of objects on the sky and in parameter space, VO-compatible exports (TOPCAT, pyVO/SCS), and a controlled in-kind ingestion pipeline for integrating externally contributed Parquet catalogues into the official QhX tables.

Main subsystems

- **PHP/Bootstrap web application**
 - *Web UI for search, object detail, visualisation modules and admin tools.*
- **MySQL / MariaDB database**
 - *Core tables (agn_objects_z, agn_coordinates, agn_bands),*
 - *Staging + in-kind upload tables,*
 - *Derived tables (e.g. agn_mass, agn_luminosity, *_feature_df).*
- **Docker-based Python validator for Parquet files**
 - *Validates in-kind Parquet uploads, enforces schema and value constraints, and populates staging tables for safe promotion to the main catalogue.*
- **VO services (TOPCAT, pyVO)**
 - *VOTable export endpoint for TOPCAT,*
 - *Simple Cone Search (SCS) endpoint for pyVO, with JWT-based token access.*

User roles

- **Scientist** – can log in via Google/ORCID, use QhX search, visualisation and VO export tools, and manage their profile and history.
 - **In-kind lead** – a scientist (or admin) additionally listed in `inkind_leads`; can upload Parquet batches, run in-kind checks, send accepted batches to staging, and review in-kind contributions in their scope.
 - **Admin** – full portal administrator; can see all in-kind batches, perform final promotion to the main tables, manage roles, and configure system-level options.
 - **Citizen Scientist** – default entry-level account created on first login. At the current stage this role can authenticate (Google / ORCID) and manage basic profile settings, but does not have access to the internal AGN catalogue tools or VO exports. The exact subset of safe, de-identified data for citizen scientists will be defined in a future iteration of the portal.
-

1. Scope and Architecture Overview

The QhX / AGN Catalogue Portal is a PHP-based web application that provides:

- Web UI for:
 - catalogue search and browsing (QhX search, browse catalogue),
 - token-based data export (TOPCAT, pyVO/SCS),
 - role & access management (admin UI).
- VO-compatible export endpoints:
 - VOTable for objects + bands (for TOPCAT),
 - Simple Cone Search (SCS) endpoint for pyVO.

- Infrastructure for in-kind contributions and controlled ingestion into the official QhX catalogue ([agn_objects_z](#)).

Technology stack:

- Backend: PHP 8.x, PDO (MySQL/MariaDB).
- DB: MySQL or MariaDB, UTF-8.
- Frontend: Bootstrap 5-based templates, simple JS helpers.
- External tools: TOPCAT, pyVO (Python), Aladin / Aladin Lite (interactive sky visualisation of QhX objects).
- External authentication providers: Google OAuth 2.0, ORCID OAuth.

Configuration is split across PHP config files in a non-public directory (e.g. sikrit1/):

- one file for database connection settings,
- one or more files for JWT secrets and other API / OAuth credentials.

Figure 1 – High-level architecture of the QhX / AGN Catalogue Portal.

The browser communicates with the PHP/Bootstrap web application, which handles authentication, business logic and VO endpoints, reads and writes data in the MySQL/MariaDB database (core, staging and derived tables), and invokes the Docker-based Python validator for in-kind Parquet uploads, while external VO tools (TOPCAT, pyVO) access the same data through dedicated VO services.

2. Data Model (Technical)

Database table inventory:

- **Core catalogue tables**
 - agn_objects_z
 - agn_coordinates
 - agn_bands

- **In-kind & staging tables**
 - inkind_upload_batches
 - inkind_upload_files
 - agn_objects_z_stage
 - agn_coordinates_stage
 - agn_bands_stage
 - agn_stage_promotion_audit
- **User & authentication tables**
 - users
 - login_audit
 - user_terms_acceptance
 - access_requests
 - inkind_leads
- **Export & VO audit tables**
 - export_tokens
 - export_audit
- **Derived / auxiliary tables**
 - agn_mass
 - agn_luminosity
 - g_feature_df
 - r_feature_df
 - i_feature_df
 - z_feature_df
 - raw_outputs_fdr

2.1 Core catalogue tables

agn_objects_z

Canonical AGN catalogue table at the object level. All scientific queries (search, VO exports, etc.) read from this table.

Typical columns (not exhaustive):

- **object_id** – primary key / unique object identifier.
- **z_adopted** – adopted redshift.
- **best_period** – best variability period (days).

- `per_err_lo`, `per_err_up`, `per_err_sym` – asymmetric and symmetric period uncertainties.
- `per_err_source` – source / method used for the period and its uncertainties (e.g. name of the code or pipeline variant).
- `t_obs_days` – effective observing baseline or total time-span covered by the light curves (days).
- `snr` – global signal-to-noise indicator for the variability detection.
- `per_err_note` – free-text note related to the period estimate and its uncertainties.
- `verdict` – classification / reliability label, e.g. `reliable`, `medium`, `discarded`.
- `bucket` – internal bucket tag (e.g. for binning / selection).
- `n_good`, `n_coherent` – counts of good / coherent bands.
- `med_snr`, `med_R2` – median SNR and R^2 across bands.
- `max_lag`, `baseline_days` – time-series baseline metrics.
- `created_at` – timestamp when the row was first inserted.

Note: The schema may be extended with additional scientific parameters over time; all new endpoints should treat `agn_objects_z` as the canonical object-level source.

`agn_coordinates`

Coordinates per object (1:1 with `agn_objects_z` by `object_id`):

- `object_id` – FK to `agn_objects_z.object_id`.
- `coord_ra_1` – RA (degrees).
- `coord_dec_1` – Dec (degrees).
- (Optionally more columns later, e.g. multiple coordinate systems.)

This table is the **driver for spatial queries**, especially cone searches.

agn_bands

Per-band metrics (1:N per object):

- `id` – primary key (auto-increment).
- `object_id` – FK to `agn_objects_z.object_id`.
- `band` – band label (G, R, I, Z,...).
- `period_days`, `amp_mag`, `phase_cycle`, `n_points_used`, `median_err`, `amp_snr`, `R2`, ...
- `ref_band`, `ref_phase`, `phase_lag_vs_ref`.
- `good_band`, `coherent_band`.
- `best_period`, `per_err_lo`, `per_err_up`, `per_err_sym`.
- `verdict`, `bucket`.

Used whenever an export requires **band-resolved** metrics.

2.2 Export & audit tables

export_tokens

Stores all JWT-based export tokens issued by the system.

Key columns:

- `id` – primary key (auto-increment).
- `jti` – unique token ID.
- `user_id` – FK to users table (not detailed here).

- `token_hash` – SHA-256 hash of the **full raw JWT** (integrity check).
- `scope` – token scope, e.g.:
 - `export:vot` – VOTable exported via TOPCAT endpoint.
 - `export:scs` – SCS (pyVO) token.
 - `export:any` – reserved for potential future combined use.
- `filters_json` – JSON-encoded filters and metadata (for audit / reproducibility).
- `ip_lock` – IP address lock for some scopes (e.g. TOPCAT URL).
- `one_time` – 1 if the token is one-time; 0 otherwise.
- `used_at` – timestamp when token was consumed (for one-time scope).
- `revoked_at` – optional manual revocation timestamp.
- `issued_at`, `expires_at` – validity window.

`export_audit`

Tracks actual data exports.

Columns include:

- `jti`, `user_id`,
- `ts` (timestamp of export),
- `client_ip`,
- `format` (`vot`, `csv`, `scs`),
- `rows_returned`.

2.3 Terms of Use acceptance audit

user_terms_acceptance

Stores the legal acceptance of the current Terms of Use (and associated Privacy Notice) per user and per version.

Typical columns:

- `id` – primary key.
- `user_id` – FK to `users.id`.
- `terms_version` – string identifier of the legal package (e.g. `2025-12-01-v1`).
- `accepted_at` – timestamp of acceptance.
- `ip_address` – optional binary IP address of the client.
- `user_agent` – optional user-agent string (for audit purposes).

A UNIQUE constraint on (`user_id`, `terms_version`) ensures one row per user and terms version.

2.4 User & access-control tables

users

Core user table for all portal accounts (citizen scientists, scientists, admins).

Typical columns:

- `id` – primary key (INT UNSIGNED).
- `email` – user e-mail address (unique index).
- `name` – display name shown in the UI.
- `user_role` – effective role of the account (e.g. `admin`, `scientist`, `pending_scientist`, ...).
- `provider` – OAuth identity provider (`google` or `orcid`).

- `provider_user_id` – stable identifier from the provider (e.g. Google subject ID or ORCID iD).
- `id_token_sub` – subject (`sub`) claim from the most recent ID token (for audit/troubleshooting).
- `access_token` – last issued OAuth access token (if stored).
- `refresh_token` – OAuth refresh token (if available).
- `token_expires_at` – expiry timestamp of the current access token.
- `created_at` – when the user record was first created.
- `updated_at` – last update of the user record.
- `last_login_at` – timestamp of the last successful login.
- `last_login_ip` – binary IP address of the last successful login (VARBINARY(16)).
- `approved_at` – timestamp when the account was manually approved / promoted (if applicable).

This table is the main source of truth for user identity and role, as referenced throughout §3 (Roles and Access Control).

`login_audit`

Audit log of login events per user and provider.

Typical columns:

- `id` – primary key (BIGINT UNSIGNED).
- `user_id` – FK to users.id.
- `provider` – identity provider used for this event (`google` or `orcid`).
- `event` – type of event (`login_success` or `login_failed`).
- `event_at` – timestamp of the event (indexed for time-based queries).

- `ip` – binary IP address of the client (VARBINARY(16)).
- `user_agent` – user-agent string of the client (up to 512 characters).

This table is used for security/audit purposes (e.g. investigating suspicious login activity).

inkind_leads

Defines which users have the in-kind lead capability.

Typical columns:

- `user_id` – primary key and FK to users.id (one row per in-kind lead).
- `granted_at` – timestamp when in-kind lead privileges were granted.
- `granted_by` – FK to users.id of the admin who granted the privileges (nullable).
- `note` – short note explaining the context or scope of the grant.

Presence of a row in this table is used as the `is_inkind_lead` flag in the application logic (see §8 for the in-kind pipeline).

access_requests

Stores formal access requests from users who want to be promoted to a higher-access role (e.g. from pending_scientist to scientist).

Typical columns:

- `id` – primary key (BIGINT).
- `user_id` – FK to users.id (requesting user).
- `orcid_id` – ORCID identifier as entered in the request (string form).
- `institution` – institution name provided by the requester.
- `inst_email` – institutional e-mail address (if provided).
- `note` – free-text note or motivation from the user.

- **status** – request status (**pending**, **approved**, **rejected**).
- **created_at** – when the request was submitted (indexed).
- **reviewed_at** – when the request was processed (approved / rejected).
- **reviewed_by** – FK to `users.id` of the reviewer (admin / scientist).
- **decision_note** – short internal note explaining the decision.
- **ip** – binary IP address of the client at the time of request (`VARBINARY(16)`).
- **ua** – user-agent string of the client at the time of request (ua = user agent).

This table underpins the “request access” flow described in the access-control and onboarding logic.

2.5 In-kind ingestion & staging tables

These tables support the in-kind upload, validation, staging and promotion workflow (see §8 for the high-level pipeline).

2.5.1 **inkind_upload_batches**

Central tracking table for all in-kind upload batches.

Typical columns:

- **id** – primary key (`BIGINT UNSIGNED`), batch identifier.
- **user_id** – FK to `users.id` (uploader; may be NULL if not resolved).
- **status** – current batch status (`ENUM`), e.g.:
 - **validated** – Python/Docker validation currently running,
 - **staged** – validated data written into staging tables,
 - **imported** – data promoted into main catalogue tables,
 - **rejected** – batch manually rejected.

- **label** – optional short label for the batch (free-text, e.g. “DP0 test sample”).
 - **notes** – batch key string associated with this upload (internal identifier used by the in-kind team).
 - **rows_coordinates** – number of coordinate rows in staging for this batch.
 - **rows_objects_z** – number of object-level rows in staging for this batch.
 - **rows_bands** – number of per-band rows in staging for this batch.
 - **error_summary** – short text summary of validation errors (if any).
 - **created_at** – timestamp when the batch was created (indexed).
 - **validated_at** – when validation finished successfully.
 - **staged_at** – when rows were written into staging tables.
 - **imported_at** – when data from this batch was promoted into the main tables.
 - **rejected_at** – when the batch was rejected.
 - **rejected_reason** – free-text explanation of why the batch was rejected.
-

2.5.2 **inkind_upload_files**

Stores metadata and validation results per uploaded file within a batch.

Typical columns:

- **id** – primary key (BIGINT UNSIGNED).
- **batch_id** – FK to `inkind_upload_batches.id`.
- **file_type** – logical role of the file (ENUM: `coordinates`, `objects_z`, `bands`).
- **original_name** – original filename as uploaded by the user.
- **stored_path** – internal path/filename on the server.

- `size_bytes` – file size in bytes (if known).
- `sha256` – SHA-256 checksum of the stored file (for integrity checks).
- `validation_ok` – boolean flag (TINYINT(1)) indicating whether per-file validation passed.
- `validation_log` – textual log / messages produced by the validator for this file.
- `row_count` – number of logical rows read from the file (if determined by the validator).
- `created_at` – timestamp when the file record was created.

Each file belongs to exactly one batch. Batches with multiple files (e.g. separate coordinates, objects and bands files) will have multiple `inkind_upload_files` rows.

2.5.3 Staging tables: `agn_objects_z_stage`, `agn_coordinates_stage`, `agn_bands_stage`

These staging tables mirror the structure of the main scientific tables, with an additional `batch_id` column to link rows to an in-kind upload batch.

Common characteristics:

- **`agn_objects_z_stage`**
 - Object-level staging table, structurally aligned with `agn_objects_z` (see §2.1).
 - Additional column:
 - `batch_id` – FK to `inkind_upload_batches.id` (indexed).
- **`agn_coordinates_stage`**
 - Coordinate staging table, structurally aligned with `agn_coordinates` (see §2.1).
 - Additional column:
 - `batch_id` – FK to `inkind_upload_batches.id` (indexed).

- **agn_bands_stage**
 - Per-band staging table, structurally aligned with **agn_bands** (see §2.1).
 - Additional column:
 - **batch_id** – FK to **inkind_upload_batches.id** (indexed).

In other words, for each of the main catalogue tables there is a corresponding staging table with the **same scientific columns**, plus **batch_id**. The Python/Docker validation pipeline writes its validated output into these staging tables, and the admin-side promotion step copies/merges the rows into **agn_objects_z**, **agn_coordinates** and **agn_bands**.

Example (for **agn_bands_stage**):

- Same domain columns as **agn_bands**:
 - **object_id**, **band**, **period_days**, **amp_mag**, **phase_cycle**, **n_points_used**, **median_err**, **amp_snr**, **R2**, **ref_band**, **ref_phase**, **phase_lag_vs_ref**, **good_band**, **coherent_band**, **best_period**, **per_err_lo**, **per_err_up**, **per_err_sym**, **verdict**, **bucket**.
- Plus:
 - **id** – primary key (BIGINT UNSIGNED),
 - **batch_id** – FK to **inkind_upload_batches.id**.

2.5.4 **agn_stage_promotion_audit**

Audit table for promotions from staging into the main catalogue tables.

Typical columns:

- **id** – primary key (BIGINT UNSIGNED).
- **object_id** – object identifier affected by the promotion (BIGINT UNSIGNED, indexed).

- `batch_id` – FK to `inkind_upload_batches.id` indicating which batch triggered the change (indexed).
- `admin_id` – FK to `users.id` for the admin who executed the promotion (indexed).
- `change_type` – type of change (`insert` or `update`).
- `old_objects_json` – JSON snapshot of the previous object-level row (from `agn_objects_z`) before the change, if any.
- `old_coordinates_json` – JSON snapshot of previous coordinates (from `agn_coordinates`), if any.
- `old_bands_json` – JSON snapshot of previous band-level rows for this object (from `agn_bands`), if any.
- `new_objects_json` – JSON snapshot of the new object-level row after promotion.
- `new_coordinates_json` – JSON snapshot of new coordinates after promotion.
- `new_bands_json` – JSON snapshot of new band-level rows after promotion.
- `is_large_delta` – boolean flag (TINYINT(1)), reserved for future logic to mark “large” catalogue changes; currently not populated by the promotion code.
- `changed_at` – timestamp when the promotion for this object was executed.

This table provides a full audit trail of how in-kind data modifies the main catalogue, making it possible to reconstruct or inspect the state before and after promotion for individual objects.

2.6 Derived feature and auxiliary tables

Besides the core catalogue tables described above, the database also contains several derived products that are used for exploration, prototype analysis and future extensions of the catalogue.

AGN mass and luminosity tables (`agn_mass`, `agn_luminosity`)

Tables such as ``agn_mass`` and ``agn_luminosity`` store additional physical quantities derived from the core catalogue (e.g. using ``z_adopted`` and other assumptions / calibrations).

Note: `agn_mass` and `agn_luminosity` are not part of the official LSST DP1 release; they are derived products computed by the SER-SAG-S1 in-kind team (see Kovačević et al., in prep.).

Per-band feature tables

Tables such as:

- `g_feature_df`
- `r_feature_df`
- `i_feature_df`
- `z_feature_df`

store time-series features computed per band (e.g. Feets-based variability descriptors) for objects in the catalogue.

Note: These features are not part of the official LSST DP1 release, but are derived products computed by the SER-SAG-S1 in-kind team using the Feets library.

Raw Outputs with False Discovery Rate `fdr_pass`

The portal includes an auxiliary “raw outputs” table that stores QhX inference summary metrics and **false discovery rate (FDR)** acceptance flags per object (`q_value`, `fdr_pass`, `verdict`, and supporting counters).

These tables are used internally for testing, exploratory analysis and potential machine-learning workflows. They are not currently exposed through the public VO endpoints or the main QhX search UI.

3. Roles and Access Control (Technical)

Roles are stored with the user (e.g. `user_role`), and enforced via helper functions in `auth_guard.php` and `post_login.php`:

- `require_role(['admin', 'scientist'])` – gate for scientific tools.
- Admin-only pages use `require_role(['admin'])`.

Effective roles:

- `admin` – full access to catalogue tools, exports, and administrative actions.
- `scientist` – access to QhX search, exports, pyVO tools, profile and search history.
- `citizen_scientist` – baseline account with minimal access (future extension).
- `In-kind flag` – not a separate role, but a property attached to a Scientist, enabling upload/validation tools.

Login and OAuth callback handling

Login is handled via Google OAuth 2.0 and ORCID OAuth:

- provider-specific callback scripts (for Google and ORCID) handle the OAuth redirect,
- a shared post-login handler (e.g. `finish_login_and_redirect()` in `auth_postprocess.php`) creates or updates the user record and applies role-based redirects.

On first successful login, a user with no existing record is created with `user_role = 'pending_scientist'`. An admin (or designated reviewer) can later promote the account to *scientist* and, if needed, grant in-kind lead capability.

Terms of Use acceptance

After a successful OAuth login, the portal checks whether the user has accepted the current Terms of Use.

The check is implemented in `finish_login_and_redirect()` and uses the `user_terms_acceptance` table plus a `CURRENT_TERMS_VERSION` constant (defined in `terms_helper.php`).

If the current version has not been accepted, the user is redirected to `accept_terms.php`, which records the acceptance and then forwards them to the appropriate dashboard based on their role.

After the Terms of Use are accepted for the first time, new users are shown a one-time role preference step where they can either remain **Citizen Scientist** or submit a request for **Scientist** access (available only to users with LSST data rights), after which they are redirected to the appropriate dashboard.

Account profile page

`profile.php` provides a consolidated account view:

- displays role/status (e.g. `pending_scientist` / `scientist` / `admin`) and linked identity provider(s) (Google/ORCID)
- includes an **Activity / Usage History** section showing the user's recorded **TOPCAT / pyVO queries and exports** (what was accessed/exported and when)
- each activity row offers a “**Details**” action that opens a modal with the **full request metadata as JSON** (raw parameters / payload, stored as audit detail)

Admin governance and audit surface

Admin pages (gated by `require_role(['admin'])`) provide governance over access and catalogue promotion workflows, including:

- role and access management (approve/reject scientist requests; promote/demote; block users)
- in-kind lead membership management (grant/revoke upload/review capability)
- review/approval actions for staged data promotion into main catalogue tables
- promotion audit visibility (batch/object-level review trail)

VO / query usage tracking (TOPCAT / pyVO)

The portal can optionally record **VO access and export usage** to support:

- system load monitoring and abuse prevention
- in-kind contribution reporting
- reproducibility and review of query activity

Tracking can include timestamp, `user_id`, endpoint (SCS / VOTable export endpoints), query parameters (or hash), row counts, and best-effort client identification (e.g. TOPCAT/pyVO via headers).

Action	Citizen Scientist	Scientist	In-kind lead*	Admin
Use QhX search and standard VO exports	-	✓	✓	✓
View own in-kind batches	-	-	✓	✓
Upload new in-kind batch (Parquet files)	-	-	✓	✓
Trigger validation / run "Check readiness"	-	-	✓	✓
Send batch to staging	-	-	✓	✓
View all in-kind batches	-	-	(configurable; typically own)	✓
Import staged data into main catalogue	-	-	-	✓
Reject batch	-	-	-	✓
View and search promotion audit (stage log)	-	-	(for scoped batches, read-only)	✓
Manage roles and in-kind lead membership	-	-	-	✓

Table 1 – Summary of actions and permissions by role.

*In-kind lead = scientist (or admin) who additionally appears in the `inkind_leads` table and therefore has access to the in-kind upload and review tools for the agreed collaboration scope.

4. Web Modules

4.1 QhX search (`qhx_object_selection.php`)

Purpose:

Interactive search over the AGN catalogue with a wide (one-row-per-object) result table, registry-based column labeling/tooltips, and aligned CSV/VOTable exports.

Access control:

```
require_role(['admin', 'scientist']);
```

Field registry integration:

The page loads `sikrit1/qhx_fields_registry.php` and flattens the registry (including band-wide aliases such as `g_*`, `r_*`, etc.) using `qhx_fields_flatten(true, $bands)`. Registry metadata is used to render **user-friendly column titles, units, schema hints, and tooltips**, while preserving stable internal aliases (shown under each header).

Input parameters (via `$_GET`):

- `q` – object ID substring (partial match)
- `minP`, `maxP` – minimum / maximum period (days), applied on `o.best_period`
- `ra`, `dec`, `radius` – cone search parameters (radius in arcseconds)
- `page` – pagination
- `format` – optional export trigger: `csv` or `votable`
- `includeBands` – optional export mode flag:
 - omitted/0 → objects-only export
 - 1 → objects + per-band rows (long-form export)

Search execution conditions:

- `$hasCone = ($ra !== null && $dec !== null && $radius_m !== null && $radius_m >= 0);`
- `$hasBasic = ($q !== '' || $minP !== null || $maxP !== null);`
- `$doSearch = ($hasCone || $hasBasic);`

WHERE clause construction:

- `o.object_id LIKE ?` for `q`
- numeric constraints on `o.best_period` for `minP/maxP`
- cone search implemented via a spherical angular-distance expression using `c.coord_ra_1`, `c.coord_dec_1` (radius converted from arcsec to degrees)

Dynamic wide-row SELECT (one row per object):

To keep the UI flexible as the schema evolves, the page discovers columns dynamically from:

- `agn_objects_z` (aliased as `obj_*`)
- `agn_coordinates` (keeps native names such as `coord_ra_1`, `coord_dec_1`)
- `agn_mass` (aliased as `mass_*`)
- `agn_bands` pivoted into **band-wide columns** using conditional aggregation:
 - for each band in `['u', 'g', 'r', 'i', 'z', 'y']` and each band metric column in `agn_bands`, creates aliases like `g_period_days`, `r_amp_mag`, `i_R2`, etc.

Band pivot pattern:

- `MAX(CASE WHEN b.band = 'g' THEN b.<col> END) AS g_<col>`

Pagination strategy (performance):

1. Count total objects matching filters (`COUNT(*)` on objects + coordinates).
2. Fetch only `object_ids` for the requested page (ordered by verdict/coherence/snr).
3. Fetch wide rows for those IDs with joins to coordinates/mass/bands, `GROUP BY o.object_id`.

Output:

- Paginated HTML table with:
 - `object_id` linked to `agn_object_detail.php?object_id=...`
 - wide object/coord/mass fields
 - band-wide columns (`u_*`, `g_*`, `r_*`, `i_*`, `z_*`, `y_*`) rendered with per-cell band styling
 - registry-based header titles + units + hover tooltips
 - an additional UI-only column `view_features` linking to: `agn_features.php?object_id=...`
- Verdict and bucket shown as badge labels.

Exports (aligned with current UI filters):

Export is enabled **only after** at least one filter is provided (basic filter or full cone search). Triggered by `format=csv|votable` and uses the same filters as the current search.

Two export modes:

1. **Objects-only** (default): objects + coordinates + mass (one row per object)
2. **Objects + bands (long form)** (`includeBands=1`): one row per (`object_id`, `band`) with selected per-band metrics, plus object/coord/mass fields repeated per row.

VOTable exports use a fixed `<FIELD>` list (datatype/unit) matching the export column set.

4.2 QhX Catalogue - Browse Data (`qhx_all_objects.php`)

Purpose:

Browse the full QhX catalogue in a wide, one-row-per-object table with quick filters, registry-based column labels/tooltips, and aligned CSV/VOTable exports.

Access control:

```
require_role(['admin', 'scientist']);
```

Field registry integration:

Loads `sikrit1/qhx_fields_registry.php` and flattens it via `qhx_fields_flatten(true, $bands)` to render column titles/units/tooltips while keeping stable internal aliases.

Input parameters (via `$_GET`):

- `q` – search by `object_id` substring; if non-numeric, treated as shorthand for `verdict` or `bucket`
- `verdict` – exact match (`reliable|medium|discarded`)
- `bucket` – exact match (`pseudo|transient|red_noise`)
- `minP`, `maxP` – period range (days), applied to `o.best_period`
- `page` – pagination
- `format` – export trigger: `csv` or `votable`
- `includeBands` – export mode:
 - omitted/0 → objects-only export

- 1 → objects + per-band rows (long-form export)

Query / table construction (wide rows):

- Discovers columns dynamically from `agn_objects_z`, `agn_coordinates`, `agn_mass`, `agn_bands`.
- Builds a wide SELECT in fixed order: `object_id` → coordinates → `obj_*` → `mass_*` → band-pivot columns.
- Band pivot columns are created for each band in `['u', 'g', 'r', 'i', 'z', 'y']` using:
`MAX(CASE WHEN b.band='g' THEN b.<col> END) AS g_<col>`.

Pagination strategy (performance):

1. `COUNT(*)` on `agn_objects_z` with current filters
2. fetch only `object_id` for the requested page (ordered by verdict/coherence/snr)
3. fetch wide rows only for those IDs and pivot bands with `GROUP BY o.object_id`

Output:

- Paginated HTML table with:
 - `object_id` linking to `agn_object_detail.php?object_id=...`
 - UI-only column `view_features` linking to `agn_features.php?object_id=...`
 - verdict/bucket rendered as badges
 - band-wide columns (`u_*` ... `y_*`) optionally styled by band

Exports (aligned with current filters):

Triggered by `format=csv|votable`, with two modes:

- **Objects-only:** objects + coordinates + mass (one row per object)
 - **Objects + bands (long form, includeBands=1):** one row per (`object_id`, `band`) including selected band metrics; object/coord/mass repeated per row
VOTable uses a fixed `<FIELD>` list (datatype/unit) matching the chosen export schema.
-

4.3 TOPCAT Export UI (`topcat_export.php`)

Purpose: Wizard to generate a **short-lived, one-time** TOPCAT URL with a JWT token.

Key steps:

1. **Roles:** `require_role(['admin', 'scientist'])`.
2. **Input fields (GET):**
 - Same filters as QhX search: `q`, `minP`, `maxP`, `ra`, `dec`, `radius`.
 - `band` – optional band filter (G, R, I, Z...).
 - `allow_all` – 1 to explicitly export the entire dataset.
 - `generate` – present if the user clicked “Generate”.
3. **Validation:**
 - If no filters and `allow_all` is not checked → error:

“No filters set. Check ‘Include entire dataset’ if you intentionally want all data.”
4. **JWT construction:**
 - Signed using HS256 with `$astro_export_secret` from config.
 - Payload contains:

- `jti` (random UUID-like),
- `sub` (user ID),
- `role`,
- `scope = 'export:vot'`,
- `filters` – JSON of the frozen filter values,
- `exp` – 15 minutes expiry.

5. DB insert (`export_tokens`):

```
INSERT INTO export_tokens
(jti, user_id, token_hash, scope, filters_json, ip_lock, one_time,
issued_at, expires_at)
VALUES
(..., hash('sha256',$jwt), 'export:vot', ..., :ipLock, 1, NOW(),
FROM_UNIXTIME(:exp))
```

- `ip_lock` = client IP.
- `one_time` = 1.

6. Generated URL:

- Built from dynamic `base_url()` (detects http/https + host).
- Format:
`https://.../vo/export_for_topcat.php?token=<JWT>`

7. UI output:

- Shows the URL,
- “Copy” button (clipboard),

- “Open in new tab” button,
- Short instruction for TOPCAT: `File → Load Table → URL → paste.`

Note: The actual responder endpoint is `vo/export_for_topcat.php`, which consumes the token and calls the helper described next.

4.4 VOTable Export Helper (`lib/agn_export_helper.php`)

Function: `do_export_votable_with_bands(...)`

- Accepts filters: `q`, `minP`, `maxP`, `ra`, `dec`, `radius_m`, `bandParam`, optional PDO `$pdo`.
- Uses `agn_db()` helper to obtain a PDO if not supplied.

Query:

- Builds a `WHERE` clause exactly like the QhX search:
 - Object ID substring,
 - Period range,
 - Cone search over `agn_coordinates`.
- If a `bandParam` is set → `b.band = ?`.

Main SELECT:

```
SELECT
  o.object_id,
  c.coord_ra_1      AS obj_coord_ra_1,
  c.coord_dec_1    AS obj_coord_dec_1,
  o.best_period    AS obj_best_period,
  o.per_err_lo     AS obj_per_err_lo,
  ...
  o.baseline_days  AS obj_baseline_days,
  b.band           AS band,
```

```

    b.period_days          AS band_period_days,
    ...
    b.bucket              AS band_bucket
FROM agn_objects_z o
LEFT JOIN agn_coordinates c ON c.object_id = o.object_id
LEFT JOIN agn_bands      b ON b.object_id = o.object_id
WHERE ...
ORDER BY (o.verdict='reliable') DESC, o.n_coherent DESC, o.med_snr
DESC, b.band ASC;

```

- The function **streams** out a VOTable:
 - Defines `<FIELD>` metadata with datatype, units, and UCD where applicable.
 - Iterates through all rows and prints `<TR><TD>...</TD>...</TR>`.
- Returns the number of rows written (for audit / logging by caller).

This is used by `export_for_topcat.php` (not shown here, but conceptually: validate token → call `do_export_votable_with_bands()` → log to `export_audit`).

4.5 pyVO Access Data UI (`qhx_pyvo_access_data.php`)

Purpose:

Interactive “field picker” for pyVO Simple Cone Search (SCS). Generates a **24h JWT token** (scope `export:scs`) and builds a ready-to-run **pyVO Python snippet** + Quick URL for testing.

Access control:

```
require_role(['admin', 'scientist']);
```

Key behaviour:

- **Registry + schema-driven columns:**
Loads `qhx_fields_registry.php` (for titles/units/tooltips) and also queries `INFORMATION_SCHEMA.COLUMNS` to list available columns from:

- `agn_objects_z` → `obj_*` aliases
- `agn_coordinates` → `coord_*` aliases (plus base `ra/dec` are always available)
- `agn_mass` → `mass_*` aliases
- `agn_bands` → band metrics used to generate wide aliases (`g_amp_mag`, `r_flux_mean`, ...)
- **User-selected fields (GET):**
 - `fields` – comma-separated alias list used to re-hydrate checkboxes
 - If no fields are selected, UI defaults to a “core” preset.
- **Cone-search inputs (GET):** `ra`, `dec`, `sr_arcsec`, `maxrec` (sticky values in UI)
- **Performance helper:** optional `band_only` (maps to endpoint parameter `BAND=<band>`) to reduce join rows.
- **On `generate=1`:**
 - Builds JWT (HS256) with payload:
 - `sub` = user id, `role`, `scope` = `export:scs`, `exp` ≈ now + 24h, unique `jti`
 - Inserts token record into `export_tokens`:
 - `token_hash` = `sha256(jwt)`
 - `scope` = `export:scs`
 - `one_time` = 0, `ip_lock` = NULL
 - `filters_json` stores UI context (`ra/dec/sr/maxrec/band_only/fields/preset/debug`)
 - Outputs:

- SCS endpoint: `.../vo/conesearch_all_data.php`
- Quick test URL with `RA/DEC/SR_ARCSEC/MAXREC/token` plus either `FIELDS=<csv>` or `PRESET=core`
- Copy/paste pyVO snippet using `pyvo.dal.SCSService(...)`

UI output:

Shows endpoint, JWT token, Quick URL, and pyVO code block, each with a “Copy” button.

4.6 SCS Full/Wide Endpoint (`vo/conesearch_all_data.php`)

Purpose:

Token-protected **VO-style SCS endpoint** returning a **VOTable** with a dynamically selected schema (wide output), including object / coordinate / mass fields and optionally **band-metric pivots**.

Error handling + health

- Converts PHP warnings/errors into exceptions; fatal errors return a minimal VOTable with:
 - `<INFO name="QUERY_STATUS" value="ERROR">...</INFO>`
- `HEALTH=1` returns plain text for monitoring.

Token-based auth

Reads `token` from `$_GET` and validates against `export_tokens`:

- Extracts JWT payload → `jti`
- Fetches token record and verifies:
 - token hash matches `sha256(raw_jwt)`

- not expired, not revoked
- scope \in ['export:scs', 'export:any']
- if one_time=1, requires used_at IS NULL
- On failure \rightarrow error_votable("...") with QUERY_STATUS=ERROR.

Input parameters

Required:

- RA (deg), DEC (deg)
- SR (deg) or SR_ARCSEC (arcsec \rightarrow converted to degrees)

Optional:

- MAXREC (default 500, hard cap 5000)
- BAND (limits joined agn_bands rows for performance)
- FIELDS (comma-separated aliases) or PRESET (min|core|full)
- DEBUG=1 adds an INFO block with summary metadata.

Validation rules:

- $0 \leq RA < 360$
- $-90 \leq DEC \leq 90$
- $0 < SR \leq 5 \text{ deg}$
- On validation error: returns ERROR VOTable and echoes RA/DEC/SR as <PARAM>.

Field whitelist + selection

Builds a **schema whitelist** dynamically from INFORMATION_SCHEMA:

- Always available base aliases:
 - `obj_id, ra, dec`
- Coordinates → `coord_<col>`
- Objects → `obj_<col>`
- Mass → `mass_<col>`
- Bands wide pivot → `<band>_<metric>` for bands `u, g, r, i, z, y` and all `agn_bands` metric columns:
 - expression pattern: `MAX(CASE WHEN b.band='<band>' THEN b.<metric> END) AS <band>_<metric>`

Selected fields are derived from:

- `FIELDS` if provided (filtered through whitelist)
- else preset:
 - `min`: minimal scientific set
 - `core`: recommended default set
 - `full`: all allowed fields
Ensures `obj_id, ra, dec` are always included.

Query strategy (performance)

- Uses `agn_coordinates` as the driver table.
- Applies **bounding-box prefilter** in RA/DEC (with RA wrap handling), then exact spherical filter using `ATAN2(...)` `<= RADIANS(SR)`.
- Joins:
 - `agn_objects_z` (required)

- `agn_mass` (left)
- `agn_bands` (left), optionally restricted by `BAND`
- Groups by `o.object_id` to support wide pivot aggregates.
- Orders by `c.coord_ra_1` and limits by `MAXREC`.

Output VOTable

- Emits `<PARAM>`: RA, DEC, SR, MAXREC, and optionally BAND / FIELDS or PRESET.
- Emits `<FIELD>` definitions in the selected order (with simple MySQL→VOTable datatype mapping).
- Rows are returned as `<TABLEDATA>`.

Audit logging

After query execution:

- Inserts into `export_audit`:
 - `(jti, user_id, ts, client_ip, format='scs_full', rows_returned)`
- If token is one-time → updates `export_tokens.used_at = NOW()`.

4.7 Terms acceptance (`accept_terms.php`)

Purpose: enforce acceptance of the current Terms of Use before granting access to any role-specific dashboard.

- Input: no query parameters; requires an authenticated session (`$_SESSION['user']`).

- Flow:
 1. If the user has already accepted the `CURRENT_TERMS_VERSION`, redirect to the stored `after_terms_redirect` target (or default scientist/citizen dashboard).
 2. Otherwise, display a one-time form with links to `terms.php` and `privacy.php` and a single checkbox.
 3. On POST, insert or update a row in `user_terms_acceptance` with the current version, timestamp, IP and user-agent.
 4. Redirect to the target dashboard.
 - This module does not change roles; it only gates access until legal acceptance is recorded.
-

4.8 Visualisation modules

The portal includes several visualisation-oriented modules for exploring the QhX catalogue. These views are intended for internal exploration, communication and method development; they are not part of the official LSST DP1 VO interfaces.

4.8.1 Interactive visualisations explorer (`qhx_visualisations.php`)

Provides a unified interactive plotting interface (2D and 3D) for rapid exploratory inspection of QhX catalogue parameters.

Data access and backend:

- Uses the JSON endpoint `qhx_vis_data.php`, with shared helpers in `qhx_vis_helpers.php`.
- Supports two dataset modes:
 - **per_object**: base table `agn_objects_z` joined with `agn_coordinates`, `agn_mass`, `agn_luminosity`, `raw_outputs_fdr`, and optional derived-feature tables (`g_feature_df`, `r_feature_df`, `i_feature_df`, `z_feature_df`).

- **per_band**: base table `agn_bands` (one row per object × band) joined with the same object-level tables.

Metadata-driven field selection:

- The UI loads a field registry (“meta”) via:
 - `qh_x_vis_data.php?meta=1&dataset=per_object|per_band`
- Meta includes:
 - a list of numeric vs. categorical fields,
 - human-readable labels (optionally sourced from `qh_x_fields_registry.php` if available),
 - axis titles and basic descriptions.

Behaviour / UI capabilities:

- User selects X/Y (and Z for 3D) from numeric fields; a “Color by” field can be numeric or categorical.
- Supports **Plotly 2D** and **Plotly 3D** rendering with:
 - linear/log scaling for axes,
 - point-size and opacity controls,
 - theme switch (dark/light),
 - color styles:
 - numeric continuous colorbar,
 - numeric binned colorbar,
 - categorical legend groups,
 - categorical mapped colorbar (integer-coded).

- Includes “Quick views” presets (e.g. Sky XY RA/Dec, Sky XYZ RA/Dec/z, Period vs SNR, logMBH vs z).

Purpose:

- Qualitative and semi-quantitative exploration of correlations and distributions across catalogue parameters.
- Not intended as a calibrated scientific plotting pipeline; results depend on selected fields and filtering/limits used for interactive performance.

4.8.2 Aladin sky map ([agn_sky_map.php](#))

Embeds a CDS Aladin Lite viewer to display QhX objects on the celestial sphere.

Data source:

- Uses RA/Dec from [agn_coordinates](#) and selected columns from [agn_objects_z](#) to build an overlay catalogue.

Behaviour:

- loads a sky background layer in Aladin,
- overlays QhX objects as markers on the sphere,
- allows pan/zoom and layer changes,
- supports inspection of individual catalogue entries via the Aladin UI.

Note:

This is a QhX-specific integration of Aladin Lite and is not an official LSST DP1 product.

4.8.3 Sonification demo: “QhX Sky Walk — Hear the Bands” ([qhx_sonify.php](#))

Interactive demo that visualises catalogue objects in a 3D point cloud (RA/Dec with a radial proxy derived from redshift) and converts each object’s multi-band properties into a short arpeggio.

Data access and backend:

- Uses [qhx_sonify_data_helper.php](#) to return a JSON payload with:
 - core fields per object: [object_id](#), [coord_ra_1](#), [coord_dec_1](#), [z_adopted](#),
 - per-band block ([u](#), [g](#), [r](#), [i](#), [z](#), [y](#)) containing:
 - luminosity medians from [agn_luminosity](#),
 - band-level QhX metrics from [agn_bands](#) (numeric + selected categorical),
 - derived features from per-band feature tables ([g_feature_df](#), [r_feature_df](#), [i_feature_df](#), [z_feature_df](#)) where available.
- The endpoint pivots band rows into a nested structure:
 - [bands\[band\].lum](#)
 - [bands\[band\].qhx\[metric\]](#)
 - [bands\[band\].feat\[feature\]](#) (only for bands with feature tables)

3D view behaviour:

- Renders a Plotly 3D scatter plot.
- Converts (RA, Dec, radial proxy) into internal x/y/z coordinates:
 - radial proxy selectable (e.g. [log10\(1+z\)](#), [z](#), [z/\(1+z\)](#), unit sphere).
 - optional “Angular zoom” scaling for visual separation (presentation/exploration aid).

- Points are typically coloured by `z_adopted` with a colorbar.

Sonification behaviour:

- Uses Tone.js + SoundFont instruments (one instrument per band) to play:
 - **single-object mode**: click a point to hear its multi-band arpeggio,
 - **walk mode**: plays a sequence of objects (e.g. sorted by redshift), moving a visible “playhead” marker through the cloud.
- User-configurable sonification mapping:
 - “Pitch source” and “Loudness source” can be chosen from band luminosity, QhX band metrics, and (optionally) derived features.
 - The UI populates dropdown options dynamically based on data coverage (fields with sufficient non-null presence).

Purpose and disclaimer:

- Outreach / exploratory module illustrating relationships between multi-band properties and survey structure through sound.
- Audible tonality is demonstrative; it is not a detection claim and not an official LSST DP1 product.
- Derived “feat.*” parameters are collaboration-provided features (not part of official DP1 releases).

4.8.4 Feature exploration ([agn_features_list.php](#), [agn_features.php](#), [agn_features_3d_plot.php](#))

These pages expose the per-band time-series features computed from light curves (Feets-based descriptors; see §2.6).

- [agn_features_list.php](#)

- Lists available feature tables (e.g. `g_feature_df`, `r_feature_df`, `i_feature_df`, `z_feature_df`) and allows navigation to per-object views.
- `agn_features.php?object_id=...`
 - Shows detailed feature values for a single object across the g/r/i/z bands,
 - reads from the corresponding `*_feature_df` tables.
- `agn_features_3d_plot.php`
 - Provides a 3D view of the feature space for a selected subset of objects,
 - allows mapping selected features to the X, Y and Z axes and, optionally, colouring by an additional parameter.

These feature visualisations are intended for internal testing, exploratory analysis and potential ML workflows. They are not exposed through the public VO endpoints and are not part of the official LSST DP1 release.

4.9 In-kind upload and lead tools (overview)

The portal includes a set of pages for managing in-kind catalogue contributions. These UIs sit on top of the in-kind data model and pipeline described in §2.5 and §8.

In-kind upload UI (scientist-level access)

Accessible to users with scientist-level permissions who are authorised as in-kind contributors.

- Allows authenticated scientists to register a new upload batch.
- Supports upload of files for coordinates, `objects_z` and bands.
- Shows per-file metadata (original name, size, checksum where available).
- Displays basic validation status per file and per batch (e.g. `uploaded`, `validating`, `validation_failed`, `staged`).

Uploaded files and their validation results are stored in the `inkind_upload_batches` and `inkind_upload_files` tables.

In-kind batch details / lead dashboard (in-kind leads and admins)

Accessible to in-kind leads (as defined in `inkind_leads`) and admins.

- Lists existing batches with key metadata (status, row counts, error summaries, timestamps).
- Provides detailed views of validation logs and, where appropriate, previews or summaries of staging tables.
- Exposes controls for:
 - rejecting a batch, with a recorded reason,
 - promoting validated data from the staging tables into the main catalogue tables.

Promotion actions are recorded in `agn_stage_promotion_audit`, which stores before/after snapshots and links each change to the responsible admin and originating batch.

These pages are tightly coupled to the in-kind staging tables (`inkind_upload_batches`, `inkind_upload_files`, `agn_objects_z_stage`, `agn_coordinates_stage`, `agn_bands_stage`) and the promotion audit (`agn_stage_promotion_audit`), but are not part of the public LSST DP1 VO interface.

5. JWT & Security Details

- **Algorithm:** HS256 (HMAC-SHA256).
- **Secret:** `$astro_export_secret` in `sikrit1/astro_config.php`.
- **Encoding helpers:** `b64u()` (base64url) and `sign_hs256()` shared between `topcat_export.php` and `qhx_pyvo_access_data.php`.

Token usage patterns:

- **TOPCAT export:**
 - `scope = 'export:vot'`,
 - `one_time = 1`,
 - `ip_lock` set to request IP,
 - `exp ~ 15 minutes`.
- **pyVO SCS:**
 - `scope = 'export:scs'`,
 - `one_time = 0`,
 - `ip_lock = NULL`,
 - `exp ~ 24 hours`.

Validation:

- Always done server-side (no trust in client-embedded payload except for `jti` to look up DB row).
 - Hash of raw JWT stored in DB; on each call, recalc and compare with constant-time `hash_equals()`.
-

6. Error Handling and Diagnostics

- All VO endpoints return **valid VOTable** even in error cases (important for pyVO/TOPCAT).

Errors are encoded as:

```
<INFO name="QUERY_STATUS" value="ERROR">message</INFO>
```

- Additional context is provided via `<PARAM>` elements for the attempted query.
 - For debugging, `DEBUG=1` on `conesearch_all_data.php` adds an extra `<INFO>` with JSON-encoded metadata (client IP, scope, row count, timestamp).
 - `HEALTH=1` on `conesearch_all_data.php` returns a quick plain-text “OK” to verify deployment.
-

7. Configuration and Deployment Notes

- Database configuration is stored in `sikrit1/astro_config.php`, while other secrets (JWT, OAuth, etc.) live in separate config files in the same non-public `sikrit1/` directory.
 - VO endpoints are under `/vo/`:
 - `conesearch_all_data.php` – SCS/pyVO,
 - `export_for_topcat.php` – VOTable export for TOPCAT (uses `do_export_votable_with_bands()`).
 - App expects HTTPS in production; `base_url()` detects reverse-proxy scheme via `HTTP_X_FORWARDED_PROTO` when available.
 - Output buffering is explicitly cleared at the start of VO scripts to avoid any stray output before XML headers.
-

8. In-kind Data Ingestion Pipeline

This section describes how external in-kind contributions are uploaded, validated and ingested into the official QhX catalogue tables (`agn_objects_z`, `agn_coordinates`, `agn_bands`).

8.1 Actors and roles

- A regular scientist (`user_role = 'scientist'`) has access to the standard QhX tools (search, VO export, profile, history). A scientist who does not appear in the `inkind_leads` table does not see any in-kind upload or lead tools.
- An in-kind scientist (lead contributor) is simply a scientist (or admin) who additionally has an entry in the `inkind_leads` table. There is no separate database distinction between “contributor” and “lead”: membership in `inkind_leads` is treated as the in-kind capability. Such a user can access the in-kind upload UI, create and manage batches, view validation results, and review batches that fall under their agreed in-kind scope.
- An admin (`user_role = 'admin'`) has full portal privileges. Admins have access to all in-kind tools and all batches, and can always perform promotion and rejection actions regardless of `inkind_leads` membership.

These roles and capabilities are enforced via `auth_guard.php` helpers (for example `require_role(['scientist'])` or `require_role(['admin'])`), combined with checks that the current user is listed in `inkind_leads`). See §3 for general role and access control details.

8.1.1 In-kind batch status flow (conceptual)

For clarity, the in-kind upload workflow can be described as a simple state machine on the batch:

- **Uploaded**
 - The batch row is created in `inkind_upload_batches`, files are stored and listed in `inkind_upload_files`.
 - This corresponds to the point immediately after the web form is submitted and initial file-level checks (type, basic Parquet structure) have passed.
- **Validated / validation_failed**
 - The Python/Docker validator runs on the uploaded Parquet files.
 - If the validation succeeds, the batch is marked as **validated** (no fatal schema/value errors).

- If it fails, the batch enters **validation_failed** with an error summary; from the UI it can then be rejected or a new batch can be uploaded.
- **Ready for staging**
 - After a successful validation, the in-kind lead explicitly runs a “Check readiness for staging” action.
 - This check ensures that:
 - the `object_id` sets in `objects_z` and `coordinates` match, and
 - all `bands` rows (if any) refer only to objects present in that batch.
 - If the consistency check passes, the batch is logically considered **ready for staging** and the UI exposes the “Send to staging” action (this is a conceptual state built on top of a validated batch).
- **Staged**
 - The “Send to staging” action reads the three Parquet files and writes valid rows to `agn_objects_z_stage`, `agn_coordinates_stage` and `agn_bands_stage`, tagged with the corresponding `batch_id`.
 - On success, the batch is marked as **staged**, with row counts and `staged_at` recorded.
- **Imported**
 - An admin runs the “Import to main” action.
 - Inside a controlled DB operation, rows from the `_stage` tables for the given `batch_id` are inserted/updated in `agn_objects_z`, `agn_coordinates` and `agn_bands`, and a detailed record is written into `agn_stage_promotion_audit`.
 - If all goes well, the batch status is **imported**, with `imported_at` set.
- **Rejected**
 - At any point after upload, an in-kind lead or admin can mark the batch as **rejected**, recording `rejected_at` and `rejected_reason`.

- Rejected batches remain in the audit trail but are not used for staging or import.

Transition logic (textual diagram):

- After **Uploaded** → run validator → **Validated** or **validation_failed**
- From **Validated** → “Check readiness” → if OK → **Ready for staging**
- From **Ready for staging** → “Send to staging” → **Staged**
- From **Staged** → “Import to main” → **Imported**
- From any state (except maybe Imported) → “Reject batch” → **Rejected**

Figure 2 – In-kind batch status and validation flow.

Three Parquet files (coordinates, objects, bands) are passed to the validator; depending on the checks, the batch is marked as *Validation Succeeded* or *Validation Failed*. A successfully validated batch moves through *Uploaded / Ready for Staging* to *Staged*, after which an authorised user (in-kind lead or admin) can either import it into the main catalogue (*Batch*

Imported) or explicitly reject it (*Batch Rejected*). At any failure point (validation or staging) and upon rejection, the flow returns to the upload stage for a corrected batch.

8.2 High-level in-kind pipeline overview

The in-kind pipeline follows these main steps:

- an in-kind scientist uploads three Parquet files,
- the system performs an initial validation and registers a batch,
- the in-kind scientist manually runs a “ready for staging” consistency check,
- only if that check passes does the in-kind scientist get the option to write the data into the `*_stage` tables,
- afterwards, an admin can promote the staged data into the main catalogue tables.

Upload

In the web UI, an in-kind scientist selects exactly three Parquet files: one with coordinates, one with object-level metrics (`objects_z`), and one with per-band metrics (`bands`).

When the form is submitted, the system performs an initial validation: it checks that all required files are present, that their type can be recognised (`coordinates` / `objects_z` / `bands`), and that each file can be opened as a valid Parquet file with the expected columns.

If this initial validation passes, the files are stored on the server, a new row is created in the `inkind_upload_batches` table, and each file gets a corresponding entry in `inkind_upload_files` (with original name, storage path, size, checksum when available, and an initial validation status). At this point, the batch status is typically “uploaded” and it appears as a new item in the batch list for that user.

Readiness check for staging

The next step is not automatic: from the batch details page, the in-kind scientist explicitly triggers a check to see if the batch is ready for staging.

This check runs a deeper consistency validation for that batch, focused on `object_id`:

- it verifies that the set of `object_id` values in the `objects_z` file matches the set of `object_id` values in the `coordinates` file (every object in one must exist in the other),

- it verifies that all rows in the bands file (if present) refer only to `object_id` values that exist in `objects_z/coordinates` for that batch (it is allowed that some objects have no bands, but not that bands reference non-existing objects).

If this check fails, the batch remains in a “problematic for staging” state:

`inkind_upload_batches` is updated with a short error summary (for example, listing the first few missing or mismatched `object_id` values), and in the UI the in-kind scientist can see that the batch is not ready for staging and should prepare a new set of files.

If the check passes, the batch is marked as “ready for staging” (status and validation timestamp are updated), and the UI exposes the next action: the option to write the data into the staging tables.

Writing into staging tables

When the batch is marked as ready for staging, the in-kind scientist can trigger the operation to send the batch to staging.

This operation reads the content of the three validated Parquet files and writes them into the staging tables:

- `agn_objects_z_stage` for object-level rows,
- `agn_coordinates_stage` for per-object coordinates,
- `agn_bands_stage` for per-band metrics.

Every row in these staging tables receives the `batch_id` so that its origin is clearly tracked.

The column structure in the staging tables mirrors the corresponding main scientific tables, with this additional `batch_id` column.

On successful insertion, `inkind_upload_batches` is updated with the row counts (`rows_coordinates`, `rows_objects_z`, `rows_bands`), the `staged_at` timestamp is set, and the batch status reflects that data are now physically present in the `*_stage` tables.

Review and promotion into the main catalogue

Once a batch has reached the staging phase, the in-kind scientist and/or in-kind lead can review a summary (status, row counts, basic metrics) and inspect samples of staging data.

Promotion into the official tables (`agn_objects_z`, `agn_coordinates`, `agn_bands`) is a separate step, typically performed by an *admin*. This step is executed as a controlled database operation (ideally within a single transaction), where:

- for the relevant `object_id` values, rows in the main tables are inserted or updated based on the corresponding `*_stage` tables for the given `batch_id`,

- `agn_stage_promotion_audit` receives a complete audit record (before/after state per object, admin ID, related `batch_id`, and the time of the change).

After successful promotion, the batch in `inkind_upload_batches` gets an updated status and the `imported_at` timestamp is set. Staging data may be retained for audit/reproducibility or later removed, depending on the agreed storage policy.

8.3 `inkind_upload_batches` table

`inkind_upload_batches` is the central tracking table for each uploaded in-kind contribution.

Typical columns (non-exhaustive):

- `id` – primary key (batch ID).
- `created_at` – when the batch was first registered.
- `user_id` – FK to `users.id` (in-kind lead who created the batch).
- `status` – current state of the batch, e.g.:
 - `validated` – validation succeeded, staging filled,
 - `validation_failed` – validation encountered errors,
 - `staged` - rows successfully written into `*_stage` tables,
 - `rejected` – manually rejected by in-kind lead/admin,
 - `imported` – data successfully promoted to main catalogue.
- `rows_coordinates` – number of coordinate rows in staging for this batch.
- `rows_objects_z` – number of object-level rows in staging.
- `rows_bands` – number of per-band rows in staging.

- `files_json` – JSON with metadata about uploaded files (original filenames, sizes, internal paths).
- `notes` – batch key string associated with this upload (internal identifier used by the in-kind team).
- `validated_at` – timestamp when validation completed successfully (if applicable).
- `staged_at` - timestamp when import to `*_stage` tables completed successfully (if applicable).
- `imported_at` – timestamp when the batch was promoted to main tables (if applicable).
- `rejected_at` - timestamp when the batch was explicitly marked as rejected.
- `rejected_reason` - short human-readable explanation recorded by the reviewer (e.g. why the batch was rejected, what was wrong with the data).

On the in-kind dashboard, each in-kind scientist sees a table with their own batches in a compact form. Typical columns include:

- batch ID (linking to the batch details page),
- created timestamp,
- current status,
- row counts in staging (coordinates / objects_z / bands, when available),
- label (short batch label),
- notes (showing the stored batch key string).

Clicking on the batch ID opens a dedicated batch details page. A typical batch detail view shows:

- header with:
 - “In-kind upload batch #<id>” and current status (e.g. Imported),
 - `Created`, `Validated at`, `Staged at`, `Imported at` timestamps (when applicable),

- row counts in the form `Rows (coordinates / objects_z / bands): c / o / b`,
- `Label` (e.g. “In-kind upload 2025-12-10 16:47:01”),
- `Notes`, where the internal batch key is displayed (e.g. `batch_key=20251211_004701_a59bb9`).
- a “Files in this batch” table with one row per file, including:
 - file type (coordinates / objects_z / bands),
 - original name,
 - stored path,
 - size in bytes,
 - SHA-256 checksum (truncated for display),
 - row count detected in that file,
 - validation status (e.g. OK),
 - a “view log” link for accessing the validation log.

For batches that have already been imported into the main catalogue, the detail page additionally exposes links or controls to view the corresponding promotion audit entries from `agn_stage_promotion_audit` (stage audit log for that batch).

8.4 Python/Docker validation and staging

The in-kind validation and staging logic is implemented in Python and executed inside a dedicated Docker container (invoked from PHP, for example via `agn_docker_helper.php` and a `docker exec` call with `--batch-id=<id>`). The current Python scripts read the uploaded Parquet files, apply schema and value checks, and prepare data for staging and potential import into the main tables.

The Python component is responsible for:

- **File-level checks:**
 - ensuring that each Parquet file matches the expected schema for its role (coordinates / objects_z / bands),
 - checking that all required columns are present,
 - confirming that column types are compatible with the MySQL schema.
- **Value-level checks:**
 - enforcing basic numeric ranges for coordinates (e.g. `coord_ra_1` in [0, 360), `coord_dec_1` in [-90, 90]),
 - enforcing that categorical fields such as `verdict` and `bucket` are within a defined whitelist (e.g. ["reliable", "medium", "discarded"] and ["pseudo", "transient", "red_noise"]),
 - enforcing non-null constraints where required (for example, `object_id`),
 - optionally computing summary metrics (row counts per table, distribution checks, etc.).
- **Relational checks:**
 - verifying that every band row references an existing object within the same batch,
 - verifying that coordinate rows are 1:1 per object for that batch,
 - verifying that object IDs are unique within each entity,
 - checking that the sets of `object_id` values in `objects_z` and `coordinates` are consistent (used in the “ready for staging” step described in §8.2).
- **Database interaction:**
 - inserting valid rows into the staging tables (`agn_objects_z_stage`, `agn_coordinates_stage`, `agn_bands_stage`) with the appropriate `batch_id`,
 - computing and recording row counts and optional summary metrics that are later written into `inkind_upload_batches`,
 - exiting with a non-zero status code if a fatal error is encountered, and exposing an error message that PHP can capture.

PHP captures the result of the Python run and updates `inkind_upload_batches` accordingly: a successful run leads to updated row counts, timestamps (for example `validated_at` and/or `staged_at`) and a success-oriented status (such as `staged`), while a failure leads to `status = 'validation_failed'` and an `error_summary` stored for display in the UI.

The internal structure of the Python scripts (module layout, function names) may evolve, but their core responsibility remains the same: take Parquet input for a given `batch_id`, enforce the agreed schema and consistency rules, and populate the staging tables in a way that is safe for later promotion into the main catalogue.

9. System Requirements

Although the portal is a standard web application, this section lists minimal and recommended requirements for deployment and operation, including optional components used for in-kind validation.

9.1 Server / backend

Operating system

- A Linux-based server (e.g. Debian/Ubuntu, CentOS/Rocky) is recommended.
- Other environments (for example a QNAP NAS running Container Station with Apache/PHP and MySQL/MariaDB in containers) are supported in practice but are not the primary target of this document.

Web server and PHP

- Web server:
 - Apache 2.4+ (with `mod_php` or PHP-FPM), **or**
 - Nginx (with PHP-FPM).
- PHP:
 - **Minimum:** PHP 8.0

- **Recommended:** PHP 8.1+
- Required PHP extensions:
 - `pdo_mysql` – database access,
 - `mbstring`,
 - `json`,
 - `openssl`,
 - `curl`,
 - `session` (usually built-in).

Database

- MySQL ≥ 8.0 or MariaDB ≥ 10.4.
- InnoDB storage engine, UTF-8 (preferably `utf8mb4_unicode_ci`).
- All core tables (`agn_objects_z`, `agn_coordinates`, `agn_bands`, `export_tokens`, `export_audit`, `user_terms_acceptance`, `inkind_upload_batches`, staging tables, etc.) are designed for InnoDB.

Resources

- **Minimum** (for small-scale testing / development):
 - 2 vCPU
 - 4 GB RAM
 - 10 GB disk for DB and logs
- **Recommended** (for production with in-kind validation and VO endpoints):
 - 4+ vCPU

- 8+ GB RAM
- Separate storage for:
 - database (~tens of GB, depending on catalogue size),
 - uploaded in-kind files and staging Parquet data.

HTTPS and reverse proxy

- Production deployment is expected to use HTTPS.
 - The application's `base_url()` helper:
 - auto-detects protocol (HTTP vs HTTPS),
 - honours `HTTP_X_FORWARDED_PROTO` headers when behind a reverse proxy.
-

9.2 Docker-based validator (optional but recommended for in-kind pipeline)

For the in-kind ingestion pipeline, the portal can invoke a Python validator inside a Docker container.

Requirements:

- Docker or a compatible container runtime installed on the host.
- Configured path to Docker binary, e.g.:
 - `AGN_DOCKER_BIN` constant in `agn_docker_helper.php`.
- A running container (e.g. `AGN_DOCKER_CONTAINER = 'ubuntu-1'`) with:
 - Python 3.10+

- `pyarrow` (for Parquet),
- any other validation dependencies (e.g. `numpy`, `pandas`, etc.).

The PHP helper `agn_docker_helper.php` encapsulates:

- building the `docker exec` command,
- passing the batch ID and relevant environment,
- capturing exit codes and logs for `inkind_upload_batches`.

If Docker is not available, the in-kind pipeline must be adjusted to run the validator directly on the host (not the default configuration described here).

9.3 OAuth and external services

Google and ORCID

- A Google OAuth client (Client ID + secret) for Google login.
- An ORCID OAuth client configuration for ORCID-based login.
- Redirect URLs must match the portal's public base URL (HTTPS).

VO tools (client side)

- TOPCAT: used externally by scientists to consume the VOTable exports.
- pyVO (Python): used externally to access the SCS endpoint.

The portal itself does not depend on these tools server-side; they are mentioned here for completeness.

9.4 Client / browser requirements

The web UI is optimised for modern desktop browsers.

- Supported browsers:
 - Latest versions of Chrome, Firefox, Edge, Safari.
- JavaScript must be enabled.
- Cookies must be enabled (for session handling).

Display:

- Minimum recommended resolution: **1280 × 720**.
 - The UI is fully responsive and usable on mobile phones and tablets (down to widths of ≈768 px), but complex admin and in-kind review pages are most comfortable to use on a laptop or desktop screen.
-

10. Future Extensions / Notes

10.1 Citizen Scientist features

Citizen Scientist functionality is currently minimal (login and basic role handling). Planned extensions include:

- defining a “citizen-safe” subset of columns and objects that can be exposed without overwhelming the user,
- simplified QhX search and object detail pages aimed at non-expert users,
- task-based interfaces (e.g., classification, flags, simple quality labels) built on top of the existing catalogue,
- per-user progress tracking and lightweight export/report options for completed tasks.

These features are intended to sit on top of the same core tables, but with stricter filters and a simplified UI layer.

10.2 3σ -based change detection and quality flags

A planned extension of the in-kind promotion pipeline is to introduce **3 σ -based checks** when comparing staged data against existing rows in the main catalogue. The goal is to automatically flag batches (or individual objects) where the proposed update represents an unusually large change.

Planned behaviour includes:

- defining 3 σ -based thresholds on key scientific parameters (e.g., `best_period`, amplitude, selected variability or quality metrics),
- during promotion, comparing staged values to existing values in the main tables and computing whether the change exceeds the configured 3 σ threshold,
- marking such cases via an `is_large_delta` flag in `agn_stage_promotion_audit` (and/or related metadata), so that they are easy to identify and review,
- optionally requiring additional manual confirmation for batches with many large-delta objects before promotion is finalised.

The exact set of parameters, the way σ is estimated, and the policy for handling “large delta” cases will be defined by the SER–SAG–S1 in-kind team as the catalogue and validation procedures continue to evolve.

10.3 Live sessions and on-air conferences

A future extension of the portal is planned around integrated live sessions using a **self-hosted Jitsi deployment** on the same infrastructure. The idea is to provide “on-air” conference rooms directly within the QhX interface, so that:

- selected users (e.g. registered scientists, in-kind contributors, citizen participants for specific events) can join live sessions from within the portal without having to log in to a separate video platform,
- conference or webinar “tiles” can be advertised contextually (for example on the main dashboard or on dedicated event pages) with a clear indicator when a session is currently live,
- access can be gated by the existing role and login system (Google/ORCID), so that participation is tied to QhX user accounts and does not require additional credentials.

The exact integration pattern (embedded iframes, dedicated “live room” pages, recording and archiving policy) will be defined in a later design phase, but the long-term goal is to make live science discussions and catalogue walk-throughs available as a first-class feature of the portal.

10.4 Sonification roadmap (Outreach → Inference → Vetting)

Further development of the sonification layer is planned as a structured, multi-mode system:

- **Outreach mode (Narrative / Aesthetic):** free exploration over many objects (as in the current demo direction).
Goal: intuitive mapping to familiar astrophysical quantities (e.g., luminosity/brightness, bands, colour, redshift).
Disclaimer: sonification illustrates photometric properties and survey structure; it is not a detection claim.
- **Inference mode (Quantitative / Scalable):** a more faithful sonification designed to encode only QhX inference outputs.
Goal: represent model outputs such as period(s), uncertainty, significance, IoU, harmonics, band-consistency, and related validation metrics.
Disclaimer: audible tonality indicates QhX-reliable periodic structure under chosen false-positive control, not a standalone confirmation.
- **Vetting mode (Human-in-the-loop triage):** using people as additional “detectors” of periodic candidates alongside the computational pipeline.
Goal: enable a reviewer to quickly answer:
 - Is this periodicity robust under QhX false-positive control?
 - Is it consistent across bands?
 - Is it cadence/alias-driven?
 - Is it time-localised (transient/pseudo), red-noise dominated, or persistent?

Planned UX elements for Vetting include a **candidate list with filters and ordering**, plus a single-screen **review card per object** (compact diagnostics + audio controls) to support rapid triage and prioritisation.

Acknowledgements

A.B.K., D.I., L. Č.P., N. de B. and S.S. acknowledge funding provided by the University of Belgrade - Faculty of Mathematics (the contract 451-03-136/2025-03/200104), Astronomical Observatory Belgrade (the contract 451-03-136/2025-03/200002) and the Faculty of Science of the University of Kragujevac (451-03-136/2025-03/200122) through the grants by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia.